

Approved Proposals of the 1st FAIRagro Use Case Call 2024

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Introduction

FAIRagro is a community-driven initiative within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Our mission is to establish an interoperable and scalable research data infrastructure and services that advances FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research data management (RDM) and to support the cultural change towards collaborative RDM practices. FAIRagro aims to foster highly interdisciplinary and multiscale research in agroecosystem-related sciences, a field of immense societal relevance.

Our goal is to support agricultural scientists with FAIR RDM by building infrastructures and services tailored to their needs. Through this effort, we strive to make FAIR practices the norm, increasing openness and integrity of research. We aim to empower researchers to share their work transparently and ensure data is discoverable and (re)usable across disciplines. As part of the broader NFDI mission, FAIRagro is committed to building a scientific future where FAIR data practices are recognized, rewarded, and integrated into innovative research.

For the years 2024-2026 we provide funds for new, community driven Use Case Pilots and Projects (UCs). The funds are allocated via two Calls in 2024 and 2025. UCs are practical examples that describe and address specific challenges in RDM within agricultural sciences as well as develop and test potential solutions. They enable FAIRagro to collaboratively tackle the spatial, subject and technical diversity of agricultural data.

The first UC call took place following the FAIRagro Community Summit between June and August 2024. 12 UC applications with running times up to 24 months were submitted. Six UC applications were approved by reviewers from the FAIRagro Community Advisory Board and the FAIRagro Steering Committee.

We here provide the approved UC applications including working plans, running times, connections to the FAIRagro Task Areas, measures and deliverables:

- 1 Next-Generation Environmental and eXtended Tools for Extreme Events & Plant Resilience Assessment “NEXT-Gen-EXPERT” by A. K. Srivastava (p. 3-14)
- 2 BrAPI Integration on PSI Hardware “BrAPI4PSI” by M. C. Heuermann and K. Neumann (p. 15-21)
- 3 Increasing FAIRness of FAIRagro data through AI supported metadata enrichment by J. Fluck (p.22-34)
- 4 Linking Agrosystem Data with Socio-economic Information, “LASI” by M. Odening et al. (p.35-47)
- 5 Diving into arable weed data to link biodiversity and farming “WeeDive” by B. Gerowitt (p. 48-58)
- 6 Systematic Approaches for Efficient Data Synchronization in Horticultural Sciences “HortSEEDS” by A. Sradnick (p. 59-68)

The new UCs were linked to the FAIRagro Task Area TA1 and are now part of the newly established Measure 1.7 (NEXT-Gen-EXPERT) and Measure 1.8 (UC Pilots 2-6).

The work programs of the approved proposals are extensions to the FAIRagro Proposal DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8366884](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366884)

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1 Next-Generation Environmental and eXtended Tools for Extreme Events & Plant Resilience Assessment “NEXT-Gen-EXPERT”

Applicant: **Dr. Amit Kumar Srivastava** (Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, ZALF)

Co-Applicant institutions: TUM School of Life Sciences, Technical University of Munich (TUM), Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ), Technische Universität Dresden - TU Dresden (TUDD)

Running time: 24 months, Jan 2025-Dec 2026

Keywords: Data tools, Climate change, Extreme events, Hybrid model, Wheat

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

Developing effective adaptation strategies for crops necessitates assessing impact of climate change, frequency and intensity of extreme events across spatial scales. One key challenge in this context are weather and climate data, which are held at different infrastructures and also vary significantly in spatial resolution, temporal coverage, and have been created for different needs. This fragmentation complicates synthesising a unified climate dataset necessary for robust agricultural impact assessments. Therefore, the proposed use case (UC) "NEXT-Gen-EXPERT" aims to develop advanced digital tools and algorithms enabling unified data workflow of bias-corrected downscaled climate change scenarios at various spatial resolutions serving as benchmark for agricultural climate impact studies. The UC is supported by NFDI4Earth (and its partnering institutions DWD, DKRZ and TUDD; see section 1.2) with expertise in climate and weather data management and integration. The UC will compare impact of CMIP6 climate scenarios with earlier CMIP phases e.g. CMIP5 on wheat yields, using hybrid models across plot to regional scales capturing spatial heterogeneity and how the impact has changed (and will change in the future) with improving climate scenarios. An automated dashboard will facilitate climate scenario data extraction, model selection, mapping and analysis, enabling researchers to visualise and data use for climate and crop impact assessments. Additionally, integrating large language models for querying databases will support variable and metadata mapping. As the climate community continuously improves its climate data, an automated tool for updating impact assessments would benefit the agriculture community (e.g. AgMIP) and other sectors (ISIMIP, AgML community).

UC concept and objectives

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the proposed use case (“NEXT-Gen-EXPERT”), illustrating steps (S) from S-1 to S-6 and associated data flow

The "NEXT-Gen-EXPERT" Use Case (UC) offers a detailed approach to develop tools and algorithms for creating a unified climate dataset aimed at assessing the impact of climate change on crop yields over time. Initially, in Step 1 (S-1) (see Figure 1), diverse climate data, both modelled and observed, are gathered from various sources to build a comprehensive and robust dataset. Collaborating with NFDI4Earth's task area "2Interoperate," the UC focuses on establishing common standards and ensuring interoperability across disciplines and NFDI consortia, thus enhancing data integration and processing capabilities. Step 2 (S-2) incorporates user input to tailor the system to the specific spatial and temporal resolution requirements of researchers and policymakers. In St 3 (S-3), data extraction and processing are undertaken, including tasks such as clipping, imputation, downscaling of climate data, and statistical analysis to identify the most suitable climate models. Step 4 (S-4) involves integrating generative AI to facilitate data querying, visualisation, and export in accessible formats such as CSV and TIFF. To guarantee open access and long-term preservation, the UC connects with the NFDI4Earth (S-6) and publishes the datasets in a trusted repository (see

NFDI4Earth Onestop4All and re3data.org), aligning with the objectives to mobilise data into European and global data spaces. The UC also aims to establish cross-consortium exchange by integrating the tools and data with DataPLANT and NFDI4Biodiversity, potentially expanding the UC's outreach to plant and biodiversity researchers. Finally, in Step 5, the focus is on analysing the impact of climate change on crops by utilising hybrid modelling techniques to understand how extreme weather and changing climates affect wheat yields with improving climate scenarios providing essential insights.

Specific Objectives of "NEXT-Gen-EXPERT" Use Case are:

1. To develop advanced data workflows and algorithms, including the identification of existing gaps (such as data standards, handling data from different resources, managing very large data sets), for spatio-temporally harmonised climate and weather datasets tailored to the specific needs of crop science leveraging climate domain expertise.
2. To enable researchers from different disciplines including crop, soil and environmental (mainly climate) sciences to perform processing, extraction, visualisation, and dissemination of datasets and data products (such as maps and time series).
3. To quantify climate change and extreme event impact comparing latest CMIP6 to CMIP5 on wheat yields across spatial scales (from plot to region) using a hybrid modelling concept combining process-based and machine-learning models.
4. To facilitate the integration of domain expertise and cross-disciplinary collaboration within the consortium and beyond.

Scientific background, added expertise and preliminary work

The ZALF group (applicant) integrates process-based and data-driven models for cross-scale agricultural systems, whereas, the TUM (co-applicant) group specialises in multi-model ensembles. DKRZ (associated partner), provides the infrastructure, software, climate change scenario data, and expertise to support climate scientists with the model development and data management. DWD (co-applicant) offers meteorological services, including agrometeorological monitoring. NFDI4Earth (associated partner, represented by DWD, DKRZ and TU Dresden) coordinates cross-consortial information exchange.

Publications:

Galmarini, S., Srivastava, A.K., et al., (2024): Assessing the impact of multi- and uni-variate climate model bias adjustments on crop modeling. *Agricultural Systems*. doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103846.

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UC specification and maturity

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Climatology, Meteorology, Agro-Ecosystem management, Process-based modelling, Artificial Intelligence.
Scales	From plot to regional scale.
Data domains	Primary data: weather and climate model data, Secondary data: soil physical and chemical properties and crop specific management and crop yield data.
Data types	Tabular and Image.
File formats	csv, NetCDF, Zarr, and Geotiff.
Source data / database / repositories	World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) hosted by German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ), and Climate Data Center (CDC) and other institutional data servers at the Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD).
Processing workflows	concept, prototype and testing via use case application depicted in Figure 1 from Step 1 to 6.
Tools/software	Python, Visual Studio Code, leafmap, LLaMA3 API, and Flask.

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	<p>Advanced Data Tools and Algorithms: Currently at TRL 3 - experimental proof of concept.</p> <p>Integration of Large Language Models (LLM): Currently at TRL 2 - technology concept formulated.</p> <p>Hybrid modelling framework: Currently at TRL 3 - experimental proof of concept.</p>
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational LLMenvironment.

Self-assessment of FAIRness status quo, data quality and legal aspects

This use case will enhance the reusability of existing climate data across disciplinary boundaries and develop reusable workflows facilitating pre-processing of climate data used as crop models input used in impact assessment.

New derived datasets will be i) published in FAIR and trusted data repository (e.g. the BonaRes Repository) ii) with a globally unique and persistent identifier (e.g. a DOI), iii) described with rich metadata and keywords specifically tailored to the UC needs, iv) using FAIR vocabularies or ontologies (such as AGROVOC) in a FAIR data repository. This addresses the FAIR principles F1, F2, I2, R1, A1 and A2.

Data fitness-for-use aspects are addressed in this use case as relevant criterias with respect to climate data are formulated to address the needs of the use case and applied for climate data selection. Additionally, climate data metadata from DWD and DKRZ will be analysed for findability from the perspective of UC needs. Options will be evaluated, if the metadata of datasets can be enriched with additional metadata or keywords specifically tailored for crop modeller's search queries, addressing the following FAIR principles F2 and R1.

The advanced digital tool (NEXT-Gen-EXPERT) prototype will be available open source (e.g. at ZALF).

Expected outcomes

- An open access data tools and algorithms for accessing benchmark dataset for agricultural research and other sectors conducting climate impact studies such as biodiversity and ecosystem management, disaster risk reduction, and water resource management etc., enabling reproducibility and comparability within and across domains.
- An automated, user-friendly dashboard for data extraction, data imputation, data selection, visualisation, mapping, and analysis across domains researching on climate impact assessments.
- A proof-of-concept for the integration of large language models (LLMs) for natural language data query, facilitating data accessibility for researchers in agriculture and other domains.
- A hybrid model combining process-based and machine-learning models for climate change impact assessments.
- Guidelines and dissemination of best practices for handling and organising research data.

Involvement of UC institutions

<i>UC co-applicants</i>	<i>Specific contributions</i>	<i>Associated Steps (refer Figure 1)</i>
TUM (co-applicant)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing technical knowhow for setting up data workflows and algorithms and establishing coordination with other Use cases within FAIRagro - Providing climate change simulation results using the DSSAT-Wheat crop simulation model. 	S-2 and S-3 S-5
DWD (co-applicant)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing high resolution station based observed Climate and weather datasets - Providing Climate domain expertise and recommendations. 	S-1 S-4
DKRZ (associated partner)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing access to Climate and weather datasets for current and future climate scenarios tailored to Use case requirements. - Supporting the project partners with expertise in climate and also with expertise in technical aspects for effective understanding and utilisation of data sets. 	S-1 S-3
TUDD (associated partner)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coordinating cross-consortial exchange; facilitating interaction with actors from NFDI4Earth and review of co-funding options for its partners . 	S-6

UC - FAIRagro connection

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	UC will benefit	UC will contribute	Essential	Short explanation (in bullet points)
TA 2: Community Involvement & Networking				
Communication and dissemination		X		Ensure the findings are widely shared, understood, and utilised, ultimately contributing to its success and broader impact.
TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality				
Standards for digital resources	X			We need expertise and recommendations on open and accepted data standards, e.g. schema.org and AGROVOC
Measures for data quality and fitness for use	X	X		We need Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards enabling sharing, integration, and utilisation of climate and weather data. Provide typical applications where data quality and fitness-for-use requirements are described.
Data quality annotation and curation		X		We will annotate existing climate datasets at DWD/DKRZ with data quality information; We will publish the processed climate datasets with data quality metadata in a FAIR data repository (e.g. the BonaRes Repository)
TA 4: Services				
Central Service (~FAIRagro Portal~)	X			We need support through the FAIRagro Infrastructure services facilitating Community engagement and capacity building.
Networked RDI				
Searchable inventory of services and data	X			Explore if infrastructures from DWD/DKRZ could be integrated into the inventory of services.
FAIRagro Task Area 5: Overarching activities				
Internationalisation				
Cross-NFDI networking	X	X		Cross-consortial data, tool and information exchange; facilitating interaction with actors.

UC requirements

For successful implementation of the proposed UC, FAIRagro will play a pivotal role in facilitating:

1. Data standardisation and interoperability by implementing standards, metadata models as per Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) standards enabling sharing, integration, and utilisation of climate and weather data across different systems. (through expertise in TA 3).
2. Data quality assurance through quality control and harmonisation across scales. (through expertise in TA 3)
3. Technical support through the FAIRagro Infrastructure services in providing searchable data to improve findability (through expertise in TA 4).
4. Facilitating Community engagement and capacity building through active stakeholder involvement to tap on their requirements and comprehensive training programs. Furthermore, FAIRagro will foster collaboration and integration with other NFDI consortia (such as NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Biodiversity, etc.) and international initiatives (such as AgMIP, ISIMIP, AgML, Wageningen Data Competence Center (WDCC)), thereby enhancing the scope, visibility and impact of the Use Case. (through expertise in TA 2).

UC dissemination and Community engagement

Dissemination & community engagement

- “NEXT-Gen-EXPERT” will enhance the findability, accessibility and quality control of weather and climate data, aligning with the FAIR principles. The requirements of the FAIRagro communities will be mirrored back to the repositories of climate and weather data which eventually leads to an improvement in the data interoperability.
- The UC will lay the groundwork for integrating scientific workflows that enable and simplify automated data extraction, imputation, downscaling, visualisation, and analysis of weather and climate data. The developed tools will allow agrosystem scientists to optimise data search and quality controls, in turn improving the quality of efficiency of research work. By using these tools, researchers are more likely to adopt FAIR and collaborative RDM practices, fostering the desired cultural change.
- The UC collaborates with the Data Steward Service Center (DSSC), other NFDI (National RDI) consortia and activities to provide training sessions on handling and organising research data. This knowledge transfer directly engages the community, raising awareness and building capacity for FAIR and collaborative RDM practices.

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

Work Package 1: Access to Climate Data and collaboration (Task Leader: ZALF Supported by DWD and DKRZ; Duration: 1-12 months)

Task 1.1: Climate data curation and preparation.

- Curate and prepare the climate datasets, including observations, reanalyses, and climate model projections including CMIP5 and 6. (possibly more).
- Ensure the selection of consistent and usable data that is of the required quality, cleansed and formatted.
- Collect comprehensive documentation for the provided climate datasets, including data descriptions, formats, units, and usage guidelines.

Task 1.2: Climate data access, updates and versioning system.

- Implementation of data access controls, authentication mechanisms, and data share protocols.
- Implementation of processes for regular updates and versioning of the climate datasets as new data becomes available.

Task 1.3: Technical Support and Knowledge Dissemination.

- Support with technical knowledge and assistance to the partners in understanding and utilising the datasets effectively.
- Advice to facilitate knowledge sharing and dissemination of best practices related to climate data management and analysis.

Work Package 2: Advanced Data Tools and User Interface Development (Task Leader: ZALF, Duration: 1-18 months)

Task 2.1: Dashboard development for Climate Data Management and Visualization.

- Design and develop a user-friendly dashboard for data extraction, imputation, and analysis.
- Implement statistical methods for climate model selection and evaluation.
- Integrate mapping and visualisation tools for stakeholders to access and visualise relevant data

Task 2.2: Natural Language Processing Integration.

- Develop an Application programming interface (API) for natural language interface for non-technical users to interact with the data repository based on pre-trained Meta Llama 3.
- Implement LLM API for query processing, result generation and export in defined formats.

Work Package 3: Advanced Modeling of Wheat Yields Using Hybrid Approaches and Climate Data (Task Leader: ZALF, co-Leader: TUM; Duration: 12-24 months)

Task 3.1: Set-up model integration framework for Climate change impact assessment.

- Implement a hybrid modelling approach combining process-based (SIMPLACE-Lintul5 and DSSAT-NWheat) and data-driven models (ConvLSTM and Transfer learning).
- Simulate wheat yields under different emissions scenarios and extreme events using the processed climate data
- Quantify the differences in projected impacts between CMIP6 and earlier scenarios in the two selected states (Bavaria and Brandenburg) of Germany.

Work Package 4: Project Coordination and Dissemination (Task Leader: ZALF; co-Leader: TUM; Duration: 1-24 months)

Task 4.1: Data Governance and Outreach.

- Establish protocols and guidelines for open access to the data repository.
- Promote transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration among other Use cases, researchers and stakeholders.
- Monitor progress, address challenges, and ensure timely delivery of project outcomes.

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
M1	Completion of data curation and preparation processes, including quality checks, data cleaning, and formatting to ensure consistency and usability.	12
M2	Complete development of a dashboard and NLP interface using a pre-trained Meta LLaMA 3 allowing users to query, extract, analyse, and visualise climate data.	18
M3	Hybrid modelling framework setup for climate impact assessment for the selected regions and wheat crops	24

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
D1.1	A curated, quality-checked climate dataset package with comprehensive documentation for observations, reanalyses, and climate model projections.	6
D1.2	Updatable climate data system with version control and data sharing capabilities.	12
D2.1	User-friendly climate data dashboard with advanced extraction, analysis, and visualisation capabilities	12
D2.2	A Natural Language Processing (NLP) API for intuitive interaction with the climate data repository, supporting query processing and result export.	18
D3	A comprehensive framework for simulating wheat yields under various climate scenarios, integrating process-based and data-driven models, with impact assessments for Bavaria and Brandenburg.	24

2 BrAPI Integration on PSI Hardware “BrAPI4PSI”

Applicant: **Marc C. Heuermann**, Kerstin Neumann (IPK Gatersleben)

Additional associated partner: PSI (Photon Systems Instruments), Klará Panzarová

Running time: 10 months, Jan-Oct 2025

Keywords: PhenoCrane, high-throughput phenotyping, image data, BrAPI, PSI

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

The Use Case Pilot BrAPI4PSI will develop together with the PSI company a BrAPI integration for phenotyping images stored on PSI data bases routinely used in European high-throughput phenotyping facilities. It will be developed exemplarily for the IPK PhenoSphere PhenoCrane system, which was built by PSI for the IPK Gatersleben <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41332-4>. The PhenoSphere system currently uses proprietary data management systems to store, access, and analyse the images. Other European research institutions like the NPEC facilities in Wageningen, who also use PSI infrastructure, bought custom APIs for the PSI Fytotron software, which controls the environmental data. Thus, developing an integration of an open access standard like BrAPI would not only benefit the IPK Gatersleben, but also NPEC Wageningen and other European PSI customers like the Vienna BioCenter Core or the PhenomUK. To adhere to the FAIR principles the research data management needs to use open standards, which are MIAPPE conform, such as BrAPI (<https://brapi.org/>). A BrAPI integration would FAIRify the PhenoCrane images captured at the IPK Gatersleben and would also provide a basis to include other data like environmental data in the future. The BrAPI integration for PSI databases could then be disseminated to other European partners.

UC concept and objectives

The concept of the Pilot BrAPI4PSI seeks to FAIRify the phenotyping image acquisition of PSI infrastructure (used in several European research institutions, here in the PhenoSphere at the IPK Gatersleben) by developing a BrAPI integration of the BrAPI-Core and BrAPI-Phenotyping modules with PSI databases to allow pull requests for subsequent FAIR use of the data.

Scientific background, added expertise and preliminary work

Heuermann, M.C., Knoch, D., Junker, A. and Altmann, T. (2023) Natural plant growth and development achieved in the IPK PhenoSphere by dynamic environment simulation. *Nat Commun*, 14, 5783. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41332-4>

Heuermann, M.C., Meyer, R.C., Knoch, D., Tschiersch, H. and Altmann, T. (2024) Strong prevalence of light regime-specific QTL in Arabidopsis detected using automated high-throughput phenotyping in fluctuating or constant light. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 176, e14255. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppl.14255>

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IPK PhenoSphere with PhenoCrane,

<https://www.ipk-gatersleben.de/en/infrastructure/phenotyping/ipk-phenosphere>,

<https://ipkstories.pageflow.io/ipk-phaenosphaere-36009#was-ist-die-ipk-phaenosphaere>

UC specification and maturity

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Plant research
Scales	PhenoSphere, LemnaTec systems in glasshouses and climate chambers, other European phenotyping facilities
Data domains	plant phenotyping image data
Data types	tabular, images
File formats	.csv, .png, .tiff, etc.
Source data / database / repositories	PSI data base, PlantScreen Server, PS Scheduler
Processing workflows	Integrating the BrAPI into the PSI software to pull request the high-throughput phenotyping images

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	TRL 8
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	TRL 9

The IPK PhenoSphere is complete and the PhenoCrane system is operational. Data in the form of images of plants can be captured, stored and analysed by proprietary software solutions from Photon System Instruments, <https://psi.cz/> Brno CZ. Thus, the TRL would be category 8. The TRL after completion of the Pilot should be category 8 to 9.

Self-assessment of FAIRness status quo, data quality and legal aspects

The UC Pilot will address the Accessibility and Interoperability of the PhenoCrane image data by enabling the transfer of the data from now proprietary storage solutions onto open repositories like e!DAL PGP following the MIAPPE concept for FAIR high-throughput phenotyping data.

Expected outcomes

The outcome would ideally be an integration of BrAPI with the PSI software to enable an automatic data exchange. BrAPI is open source and could be applied by other European or also International research institutions who use PSI phenotyping infrastructure.

Involvement of UC institutions

The associated partner would be Photon System Instruments, Brno Czech Republic. They develop and sell high-throughput phenotyping infrastructure like RGB cameras, hyperspectral cameras, and chlorophyll fluorescence measurement panels together with installation and software solutions. In the UC Pilot they would integrate the BrAPI with their software as contractors.

UC - FAIRagro connection

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	UC will benefit	UC will contribute	Essential	Short explanation (in bullet points)
TA 2: Community Involvement & Networking				
Communication and dissemination	X	X		joint activity to disseminate BrAPI implementation for PSI based Phenotyping systems in Europe
Training and education	X			training on FAIR sensor data and FAIR phenotyping data
TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality				
Standards for digital resources		X		Establish links to sensor equipment vendors to define instruments metadata standards and PUIDs
Standards for data management	X	X		Make multimodal image data and sensor data accessible and interoperable. Support definition of environmental indexes towards a classification of environmental conditions in MIAPPE
Data quality annotation and curation	X	X		Contribute to quality metrics for data stream in IoT environment
FAIR workflows and FAIR Digital Objects		X		Contribute data flows for data life cycle for IoT environment sensor data. Expose HTP image data accessible and interoperable
TA 4: Services				
Central Service (~FAIRagro Portal~)	X			
Networked RDI	X	X		
Searchable inventory of services and data	X			enable FAIR PhenoCrane data and make it accessible and thus searchable

UC requirements

In plant science, the lack of coordination of phenotyping experiments in controlled environments, such as greenhouses and automated phenotyping facilities in particular, hampers reproducibility and transferability to field environments (Heuermann et al. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-023-41332-4). In particular, a transferable experimental set-up and the dissemination of results and data according to FAIR criteria is a barrier. To record phenotypic traits, the IPK has five different state-of-the-art imaging facilities. This infrastructure for plant phenotyping is of international importance. FAIRagro therefore forms a structure to create common standards and data access platforms.

Possible initial steps are to be evaluated in the pilot based on the IPK automated greenhouse phenotyping (www.ipk-gatersleben.de/en/infrastructure/phenotyping/greenhouse-systems) in order to prepare concrete options for long-term collaboration in FAIRagro structures. This will be based on the implementation of the BrAPI. Managed by an IPK employee, this should be done as a subcontract from the PSI company with the support of FAIRagro expertise. In the medium term, it may be possible to connect to the PhenoSphere climate simulation installation (www.ipk-gatersleben.de/infrastruktur/phaenotypisierung/ipk-phaenosphaere) in order to define standard operating procedures together with other high-throughput phenotyping installations and implement the FAIR data flows.

UC dissemination and Community engagement

Dissemination & community engagement

The goal of the UC Pilot is to make the image data of PSI systems FAIR and ultimately provide the open API to other European research partners or anyone who is interested.

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

Action 1: Develop an integration of the BrAPI for PSI software

Institution 1: IPK Gatersleben

Institution/ partner 2: Photon System Instrument, <https://psi.cz/>

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
M1	Develop BrAPI endpoints to access PSI data management components	10

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
D1	BrAPI4PSI, BrAPI integration in PSI software	10

3 Increasing FAIRness of FAIRagro data through AI supported metadata enrichment

Applicant: **Prof. Dr. Juliane Fluck** (ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences)

Additional associated partner: Xenia Specka (Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, ZALF), Ulrike Stahl (Julius Kühn-Institut – Bundesforschungsinstitut für Kulturpflanzen, JKI)

Running time: 12 months, Nov 2024–Oct 2025

Keywords: metadata enrichment, text mining, AI, FAIR, Research Data Infrastructures

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

High-quality metadata is essential for the [FAIR principles](#). As research data management (RDM) becomes crucial, stakeholders recognize the need for meaningful metadata and automated generation processes. These advancements ensure future metadata FAIRness but do not address legacy metadata, which lacks standardized collection practices.

FAIRagro is developing a metadata schema for harmonizing heterogeneous metadata of participating Research Data Infrastructures (RDIs) to facilitate a central search, increasing the Findability of agrosystem resources. To enable an efficient transformation of legacy metadata of the RDIs to make integration into the FAIRagro Central Search Service as efficient as possible, this pilot project tests how far state of the art AI-based text mining techniques, e.g., deep learning models and few-shot learning, are able to automatically extract relevant information from unstructured data (e.g. dataset abstracts, related publications, the data itself, etc.), using Named Entity Recognition (NER). These tasks involve identifying both general and agrosystem domain specific entities and relations. The goal of this pilot is to extract information on two different core entities (Crops, Soil) from two different FAIRagro RDIs (OpenAgrar, BonaRes Repository) and make it available in a structured way. Furthermore, it evaluates if text mining offers a viable method for enriching metadata to the schema developed for powering the Central Search Service.

The outcome will show how far AI methods are ready to make agrosystem resources FAIRer and to assist participating RDIs in extending their provided metadata in a resource efficient way. If the pilot is successful, further developments can be made to support all FAIRagro infrastructures or even other domains in metadata extension, opening up possibilities for e.g. cross-NFDI consortia collaboration in the future.

UC concept and objectives

Figure: Integration of the Text Mining pipeline into FAIRagros service infrastructure. The projects Research Data Infrastructures (RDIs) provide metadata as Schema.org markup to the Central Search Service via the Middleware, conforming to the FAIRagro Search Metadata Schema. The Text Mining pipeline collects the unstructured elements provided as metadata, prepares and preprocesses them and extracts and classifies relevant terms based on an AI model. In this way the metadata becomes enriched and will be evaluated

The developments planned in this pilot fit seamlessly into FAIRagro service landscape and helps closing a gap between the current decentralized search capabilities, the envisioned central search service and its benefits towards semantic searches and increased exposure to relevant search engines.

The main components and services for the pilot are either already in a production status and available such as the RDIs and the building blocks of the Text Mining (information extraction) pipeline, as part of ZB MEDs infrastructure, or are progressing according to the project proposal. The combination of the different components (as represented by the dotted arrow) promises an efficient bundling of resources.

The pilot will begin by analysing suitable data for the task in close cooperation with the participating RDIs. During this process the relevant documents and metadata fields will be evaluated for extraction. Annotation guidelines will be developed and used for creating a manually annotated training corpus (**Action 1.1**). The manual annotation will be done using the software INCEPTION which enables the integration of a recommender system, allows curators

to correct them, and facilitates the introduction of the main entity classes that will be annotated. This software is already installed in ZB MED's infrastructure and ready to use remotely, enabling the provision of feedback on annotations by domain experts at the RDIs (**Action 1.2**). Simultaneously a literary review will identify the most fitting model for the pilots requirements (**Action 2.1**) and prepare the following Actions by setting up the needed infrastructure for the text mining (**Action 2.2**).

After this preparation is finished, work on using the text mining pipeline for creating automated annotations and extractions will begin by using the annotated text corpus alongside the data imported from the RDI's to develop and test the information extraction pipeline. The main components of this pipeline are:

1. **Data collection:** Gathering annotated data and raw data from RDIs, storing it in an organized manner (e.g., JSON format).
2. **Data pre-processing:** The collected data is pre-processed to ensure that it is in a suitable format for the models. This involves considering the maximum text length each model can handle and performing necessary pre-processing steps such as tokenization, normalization, and removal of irrelevant data. The output of this step is tabular data containing the different texts and their corresponding annotations. Steps such as tokenization, normalization, and other preprocessing methods produce tabular data in a format fitting for training and testing the models.
3. **Models development:** The models are developed by adapting state of the art deep learning NER methods (supervised learning or few-shot learning using the annotated data as training set).
4. **Models evaluation:** The models are tested using the annotated text corpus as reference data. A comparison between the different methods and an evaluation of which parts of the metadata they perform best on will be the output of this step.
5. **Annotations export:** Export the annotated data with their spans and transfer the different entities into their place in the metadata schema.

As a final step the use-case will evaluate the extracted metadata outputs of the automated annotations and extractions by manually curating the results. Depending on an uncertainty value for the automated annotation, domain experts will assess their correctness, leading to quality results (**Action 3.1**). To benefit from the enriched metadata it has to be made available. The requirements for setting the RDIs up for these changes will be explored in close collaboration (**Action 3.2**).

All the insights won during the pilot will support the partners to develop an understanding of needed resources for large scale metadata transformation processes, giving the RDIs insight and support in decision making and planning regarding their approach toward increasing the FAIRness of their metadata collections. To make these findings available and reusable by others (e.g. other RDIs with ties to the agrosystem domain), a strategy will be devised and published (Action 3.3).

Scientific background, added expertise and preliminary work

The Knowledge Management department at ZB MED has particular expertise in text mining, semantic search, named entity recognition, and information extraction in various life science applications. Most recently this technology has been developed for publications related to the global pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2. Relevant publications by the group:

Langnickel, L., Darms, J., Heldt, K., Ducks, D., Fluck, J. (2022). Continuous development of the semantic search engine preVIEW: from COVID-19 to long COVID. In: Database, Volume 2022. DOI: [10.1093/database/baac048](https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baac048)

Sasse, J., Darms, J., Fluck, J. (2022). Semantic Metadata Annotation Services in the Biomedical Domain – A Literature Review. In: Applied Sciences, 12 (2), p. 796. DOI: [10.3390/app12020796](https://doi.org/10.3390/app12020796)

Julia Sasse, Juliane Fluck: An Annotation Workbench for Semantic Annotation of Data Collection Instruments. In: Studies in Health Technology and Informatics, Volume 302. DOI: [10.3233/SHTI230074](https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI230074)

Kühnel, L., Schulz, A., Hammer, B., Fluck, J. (2022). BERT WEAVER: Using WEight AVERaging to enable lifelong learning for transformer-based models in biomedical semantic search engines. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.2202.10101](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2202.10101)

Lentzen, M., Madan, S., Kühnel, L., Fluck, J., et al. (2022). Critical assessment of transformer-based AI models for German clinical notes. In: JAMIA Open, Volume 5, Issue 4. DOI: [10.1093/jamiaopen/ooac087](https://doi.org/10.1093/jamiaopen/ooac087)

The Information Centre and Library team and the Team FDM at JKI combine expertise in the agricultural domain with handling of domain and publication-specific metadata, subject indexing, the use of subject-specific thesauri and publishing research data at OpenAgrar in a FAIR manner. Relevant publications by the group:

Oeltjen, W., Neumann, K., Stahl, U., & Stephan, R. (2019). MyCoRe macht Forschungsdaten FAIR. Bibliothek : Forschung und Praxis, 43(1), pp. 82–90. [10.1515/bfp-2019-2013](https://doi.org/10.1515/bfp-2019-2013)

The RDM and Data Infrastructures working groups at ZALF possess extensive expertise in data publication and curation. They operate the BonaRes Repository, a RDI dedicated to the publication of soil and agricultural research data. Relevant publications by the group:

Svoboda, N., Schmidt, M., Hoffmann, C., Specka, X. (2022). Citing soil and agricultural research data. BonaRes Series. DOI: [10.20387/bonares-fm2j-c233](https://doi.org/10.20387/bonares-fm2j-c233)

Grosse, M., Hoffmann, C., Specka, X., Svoboda, N. (2020) Managing long-term experiment data: a repository for soil and agricultural research. In: Bhullar, G. S., Riar, A. (eds), Long-term farming systems research. Academic Press, an imprint of Elsevier, London, pp. 167-182. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-12-818186-7.00010-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818186-7.00010-2)

Specka, X., Gärtner, P., Hoffmann, C., Svoboda, N., Stecker, M., Einspanier, U., Senkler, K., Zoarder, M. A. M., Heinrich, U. (2019) The BonaRes metadata schema for geospatial soil-agricultural research data - merging INSPIRE and DataCite metadata schemes. Computers & Geosciences 132, 33-41. DOI: [10.1016/j.cageo.2019.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2019.07.005)

UC specification and maturity

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Computer Science, Text Mining in agriculture
Data domains	Metadata of published research data in agriculture
Data types	Text, metadata
File formats	Open, JSON, XML, txt, csv, ann
Source data / database / repositories	FAIRagro RDIs (BonaRes Repository, OpenAgrar)
Processing workflows	prototype
Tools/software	Python, Huggingface

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	TRL 3 - experimental proof of concept
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	TRL 4 – technology validated in lab

Self-assessment of FAIRness status quo, data quality and legal aspects

F2: Data are described with rich metadata: The UC will support RDIs in providing additional rich, relevant metadata, making additional search queries for finding the data possible

I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation: Developments in FAIRagros TA3 aim at using Linked Data technologies for making metadata machine readable. The UC will develop mechanisms to increase implementation uptake of these technologies.

I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles: By transforming RDI metadata to agreed upon metadata standards and increasing its structure, making interlinking the data to machine readable ontologies easier, increases its Interoperability

R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes: The pipeline developed in the UC will be used to generate metadata, that was identified as highly relevant for finding datasets by current FAIRagro use-cases, ensuring the necessity of results and orientation towards real UC needs

Expected outcomes

- Software source code of the adapted text mining pipeline
- The annotated and quality checked agricultural text corpus
- The trained machine learning models
- The generated enriched metadata resources
- A strategy giving guidance and insight for Research Data Infrastructures on how to enrich their metadata towards the FAIRagro Search Portal Metadata Schema

Involvement of UC institutions

Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research, specifically the working groups Research Data Management (FDM) and Data Infrastructures (DIS) will contribute to the UC by:

- Providing metadata from published datasets in the BonaRes Repository via existing harvesting interfaces to be used in text mining approaches in the Use Case Pilot.
- Offering data curation expertise for soil and agricultural research data to aid in developing annotation guidelines.
- Giving feedback on the derived annotations for selected datasets from the BonaRes Repository by providing domain expertise on soil- and agricultural research data

The Information Centre and Library team and the Team FDM at JKI will contribute to the UC by:

- Providing metadata from published datasets and text publication in the OpenAgrar Repository for text mining approaches via existing harvesting interfaces
- Providing annotation of data sets and evaluation of semi-automatic curation workflows regarding the training data from OpenAgrar with respect to publications from the crop and soil domain
- Defining text corpus selection criteria and annotation guidelines
- Giving feedback on the derived annotations for selected datasets from the OpenAgrar Repository by providing domain expertise on soil- and crop research data

UC - FAIRagro connection

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	UC will benefit	UC will contribute	Essential	Short explanation (in bullet points)
TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality				
Standards for digital resources	X		4	This pilot can reuse elements of ontologies and metadata standards collected in the Standard Inventory developed by M3.1 for developing the annotation guidelines in Action 1.1.
Standards for data management		X	2	M3.2 develops an extension of Schema.org as part of Bioschemas. This pilot will help increasing adoption, by offering RDIs a resource efficient way of adopting the extension.
TA 4: Services				
Networked RDI		X	1	The Middleware developed in M4.2 harmonizes the metadata of the FAIRagro RDIs and provides it for other FAIRagro services such as the Central Search Service. This pilot supports the Middleware by enriching the metadata of the RDIs, making harmonization easier.
Searchable inventory of services and data		X	3	As outlined in the short explanation of the Middleware Measure (M4.2), the Central Search Service will benefit from developments of the UC.

UC requirements

- Access to metadata of participating research data infrastructures in a format suitable for text mining methods (e.g., via the middleware)
- A list of core metadata entities that should be extracted from unstructured metadata (in cooperation with TA3)
- Support from RDIs/domain experts in creating a manually annotated corpora
- Support from RDIs/domain experts by evaluating a semi-automated curation process

UC dissemination and Community engagement

Dissemination & community engagement

The FAIR principles and the Open Science movement are key pillars of advancing research in a way that enables broader participation and sustainable growth. These developments first and foremost require a cultural change in research practices such as the openness to publish data to make it available for the public, enabling reuse by others, leading to new results and increasing the quality of research in general.

The outcomes of this use case will support such a cultural change by providing tools that decrease the work needed from researchers in achieving FAIRness for their data. Publishing research data in a reusable manner, initially takes more effort for researchers. This can lead to a decision against data publication due to limited resources even if willing to do so.

Another aspect that will foster a cultural change is that the results of this use case will demonstrate the added values of an implementation of the FAIR principles. By enriching metadata and using it to support developments such as easier adoption of the Schema.org extension of M3.2, the use case will support in making datasets more Findable and therefore more Reusable resulting in more willingness of researchers to become part of an open data community.

Workplan

Action	Months											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Action 1	M1 / D1	M1 / D1	M1 / D1									
Action 1.1	M1 / D1	M1 / D1										
Action 1.2			M1 / D1									
Action 2				M2 / D2								
Action 2.1	M2 / D2	M2 / D2	M2 / D2									
Action 2.2		M2 / D2										
Action 2.3				M2 / D2	M2 / D2							
Action 2.4						M2 / D2	M2 / D2	M2 / D2	M2 / D2			
Action 3										M3 / D3	M3 / D3	M3 / D3
Action 3.1										M3 / D3		
Action 3.2											M3 / D3	
Action 3.3												M3 / D3

Actions (Work packages)

Action 1: Analysis of data and preparation of annotated text corpora (Months 1-3)

Institution: ZB MED; Partner: ZALF, JKI

Summary: This action prepares an annotated text corpus for using it in the following actions as a resource in the text mining pipeline. To achieve this, results of this action include selection criteria for building the corpus, annotation guidelines and applying the guidelines to create the corpus.

Action 1.1: Define text corpus selection criteria and create annotation guidelines (Months 1-2)

In close collaboration with domain experts of the BonaRes Repository and OpenAgrar, a set of criteria is defined to determine which datasets and metadata descriptions to include as resources in the text mining corpus. The selection will depend on what information (e.g. metadata fields such as descriptions/abstracts) is available for each dataset.

Additionally, once the resources for the corpus are known, annotation guidelines for Action 1.2 are proposed by ZB MED and evaluated by domain experts of the RDIs. These include what entities to annotate (e.g. crops, soil types) and include annotation examples from the selected datasets to enable a common understanding and guarantee consistent quality in the following manual annotation of the corpus.

Action 1.2: Creation of manually annotated text corpus (Month 3)

The results of **Action 1.1** will be used to manually annotate the collected text corpus, following the annotation guidelines. ZB MED will provide centralized access to INCEPTION and create the corpus. Domain experts of the RDIs will evaluate these annotations to ensure their quality for the use of the corpus in **Action 2.4**.

Action 2: Automatic extraction and annotation of metadata (Months 1-9)

Institution: ZB MED

Summary: This action aims to research the most suitable AI methods for the pilot and integrate them into a Named Entity Recognition pipeline. The main steps are to conduct a literature review, decide on the candidate models to use and determine the required infrastructure to run them. Next, the data from the RDI's and other external sources is prepared, followed by training the candidate models using this data. The models are then evaluated using the annotated data. Finally, the models' outputs are made available to be used in **Action 3**.

Action 2.1 Literature Review and Model Selection for Named Entity Recognition in agriculture (Months 1-3)

This action includes a comprehensive literature review on the state of the art in Named Entity Recognition (NER) in the field of agriculture. It involves determining which current state-of-the-art models can be used directly off-the-shelf and identifying which models need further adaptation for the requirements of this specific pilot. Additionally, it defines the technical specifications required to run those models.

Action 2.1 operates in parallel to **Action 1** and its results, aiming to stay up-to-date and continuously update the list of models simultaneously. It is important to find through the literature review the number of samples per entity that is required to train models in a supervised manner (learn from positive examples) or evaluate if few-shots training (learn from few examples) is sufficient. At the same time this action is identifying additional annotated agricultural datasets in the literature which might be included in the following actions.

Action 2.2: Set up the information extraction pipeline infrastructure (Month 2)

To develop and test the models selected in **Action 2.1**, the right computational infrastructure needs to be set up. The main parts of this setup include data storage and computing power:

- **Data Storage:** Enough storage space is needed to hold all the data, and it should be connected to the computing systems for quick access.
- **Computing power:** High computational power is required to run, train, and test the advanced models. The key specifications to consider are the size of the GPU (graphics processing unit) and the corresponding CPU (central processing unit) and RAM (memory) that go along with it.

The product of this Action is selecting the suitable infrastructure and setting up all the users and the storage options to use it.

Action 2.3: Data preparation (Months 4-5)

The pilot relies on data from different RDIs and their heterogeneous data formats. This requires to process each dataset based on its source and create a unified dataset for training and testing the models. By applying a unified format and set of attributes to all data, regardless of the source, we ensure the system works smoothly and can potentially incorporate new RDI's. This approach guarantees scalability and reproducibility.

The result of this Action is a unified dataset that enables minimum steps for data preprocessing in the following step of model development.

Action 2.4: Model development and data reprocessing and evaluation of results (Information Extraction Pipeline) (Months 6-9)

Using the infrastructure established in **Action 2.2**, the design of the models using AI frameworks (i.e. Huggingface) is evaluated by executing the pipeline. Its main components are:

- **Data preprocessing:** Based on each model, different data format and different data size should be adapted to the model. The data is split into training and testing data.
- **Model parameters optimization:** Set up the model parameters for the application. These parameters vary from input/output sizes to optimization methods and cost functions.
- **Exporting output:** Make sure that the output format is comparable to the data format implemented in Action 2.3 so that it can be evaluated and compared to other models. The output of each model should be a list of entities in a format that includes their label (entity class), text, position in original text and a certainty score of the label. From ZB MED's expertise in biomedical text mining, existing pipelines can be used as reference or integrated in this step.
- **Evaluation:** Defining evaluation criteria based on matching entity labels and their spans in the text, counting correct (True Positive), incorrect (False Positive), and missed (False Negative) predictions. Common metrics used are Precision, Recall, and F1 Score. The models are then tested on the dataset, and their outputs are compared to the manually annotated text corpus from **Action 1.2** as reference data. ZB MED has existing evaluation scripts for biomedical data that can be adapted for this purpose.

The outputs of this action are:

- The model(s) that will be published
- The metadata according to the schema from **Action 1.1** and a simple prototype for a tool for curating uncertain results (for **Action 3.1**)
- The information extraction pipeline.

Consideration for the pipeline are:

- Enable continuous training on any new data that will be available in the future to improve the performance.
- It should be modular meaning all components could be adapted in other applications.
- It should be extensible, meaning that new features (i.e. new RDI's and new entity classes) could be added in the future.

Action 3: Evaluation of semi-automatic curation approaches and designing large scale metadata transformation processes (3 Months)

Institution: ZB MED; Partner: ZALF, JKI

Summary: **Action 3** uses the results of **Action 2** and makes them available in different ways. By evaluating uncertain results of the automated extraction, **Action 3.1** ensures the quality of the extracted metadata. This opens the possibility of ingesting it into the RDIs in a structured way, which will be explored in **Action 3.2**. To plan large scale metadata enrichment tasks for the future and to make the insights available for a broader community, **Action 3.3**. will develop and communicate a strategy, which other (FAIRagro) RDIs can profit from.

Action 3.1: Definition and evaluation of semi-automatic curation workflows

The extracted metadata from **Action 2.4** marked as uncertain will be evaluated by domain experts BonaRes Repository and OpenAgrar. They will decide if the extraction of the entity was accurate or not and correct it if necessary. By approaching this task in a structured and reproducible manner, it will create insight on the time and resources needed, enabling estimations for possible future use-cases and RDIs (see **Action 3.3**).

Action 3.2: Develop plan for ingesting enriched metadata into the RDIs

Once the extracted metadata has been evaluated as correct, **Action 3.2** will explore ways of ingesting it back into the respective RDI, to make it available for the users of the services. To make this possible, metadata models of the RDIs have to be re-evaluated and extended. Due to the dependencies of other services, that rely on the RDIs and orientation towards developments such as FAIRagro metadata efforts, this Action can only achieve conceptual results instead of finished implementation and will be carried out in intensive cooperation between all pilot partners.

Action 3.3: Conceptualize processes for large scale metadata enrichment

Based on the experiences made and statistics collected during the previous Actions, a strategy for enriching other datasets of the RDIs is developed. The strategy will describe requirements, estimated resources and devise a timeline for implementing the developed metadata enrichment processes on a large scale. The outcome will be published and not only support the co-applicant RDIs in enriching the rest of their collections but can also act as a basis for developing similar approaches for other FAIRagro RDIs.

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
M1	Text corpus is manually annotated following developed annotation guidelines	3
M2	Tests on automated metadata extraction and annotation are completed and enriched metadata is available	9
M3	Strategy and semi-automated processes on metadata extraction are designed and communicated	12

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
D1	Report on manually annotated training corpus is published	4
D2	Report on test results of automated metadata extraction and annotation are evaluated and published	10
D3	Strategy on semi automated metadata extraction and curation processes is published	12

4 Linking Agrosystem Data with Socio-economic Information, “LASI”

Applicants: **Prof. Dr. Martin Odening**, Prof. Dr. Timo Kautz, Dr. Günther Filler (Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, HUB)

Additional associated partner: Prof. Dr. Oliver Mußhoff (Uni Göttingen), Prof. Dr. Alfons Balmann (IAMO Halle)

Running time: 12 months, Mar 2025-Feb 2026

Keywords: Land use, Land markets, Socio-economic data, Field trials

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

LASI enhances the existing information on Agrosystems by socio-economic information and establishes a connection between those areas. In particular, it focuses on agricultural land markets, because land is the most important production factor in agriculture and the natural link between landscapes and farms. Land markets are facing unprecedented challenges, marked by a surge in land prices, intensified competition among farmers, and a concerning trend of converting farmland for non-agricultural purposes. Access to data is of pivotal importance for all kinds of research for example on regulation measures, market structures, market types and market participants as well as on price levels and dynamics, ownership distribution and on environmental and social implications. Recent socio-economic data sources differ in terms of purpose, regional coverage, time period, data type, temporal as well as spatial resolution. LASI is striving to classify agricultural land market data sources, to identify and categorize interfaces between Agrosystem-related information and socio-economic variables. LASI's primary subject is to expand the scope of FAIRagro through the development of meta-databases and technical reports. The secondary issue addresses improved transfer of knowledge gathered in long-term agricultural field trials. LASI oversees several long-term field experiments in Thyrow and Dahlem. As FAIRagro is an excellent platform for the dissemination of research activities, LASI attempts for a FAIR communication of long-term field trial data, increasing visibility and usefulness of such experiments for agricultural stakeholders.

The outcome will show how far AI methods are ready to make agrosystem resources FAIRer and to assist participating RDIs in extending their provided metadata in a resource efficient way. If the pilot is successful, further developments can be made to support all FAIRagro infrastructures or even other domains in metadata extension, opening up possibilities for e.g. cross-NFDI consortia collaboration in the future.

UC concept and objectives

Figure 1: Enhancing the FAIRagro cosmos by socio-economic information subject to agricultural land markets. Source: Own representation

HUB proposes a new use case (UC) that connects Agrosystem-related information with data on users of Agrosystems, and their socio-economic characteristics. Agricultural land markets are the subject of interest. These markets are facing unprecedented challenges, marked by a surge in land prices, intensified competition among farmers, and a concerning trend of converting farmland for non-agricultural purposes. This escalating issue has caught the public's attention, and there is a growing demand for effective governmental regulation. Agricultural land markets are characterized as a social system embedded in the natural, economic, and social environment.

Figure 1 illustrates the complexity of factors that determine the outcome of land markets. It highlights that a multidisciplinary approach is required. Concurrently, access to data is of pivotal importance for all kinds of research for example on regulation measures (e.g. market access, zoning or price limits), market structures (distinction between sales and rental markets), market types and market participants as well as on price levels and dynamics, ownership distribution and on environmental and social implications. In particular, the project focuses on (socio-economic) data structures with respect to multiple stakeholders, parties and institutions (actors like farmers, land societies, policy makers, investors), on agricultural land markets. This new UC is an amazing addition to the existing information on Agrosystems, providing a wealth of socio-economic information that was previously unavailable (see Figure 1, right part). Engaging with stakeholders and interested parties is crucial for the success and impact of a project focusing on agricultural land market data. Here's a breakdown of key stakeholders and their potential interests (also on data). Farmers ask for access to fair and competitive land prices, insights into market trends for informed decision-making, and protection from speculative practices. Investors seek for transparent data for assessing investment opportunities, understanding market dynamics, and mitigating

risks associated with agricultural land investments. Government Agencies have demand for evidence-based insights for policymaking, effective regulation of land markets, and support for sustainable agricultural practices. Researchers and Academics demand for access to a well-structured dataset for in-depth studies, contributing to the academic understanding of agricultural land markets. Environmental Organizations trust on information on land-use changes for assessing environmental impacts and advocating for sustainable land management practices. Real Estate Professionals are interested in accurate data for property valuation, market trends, and facilitating transparent real estate transactions in the agricultural sector. Legal and Regulatory Bodies want to ensure compliance with data protection laws, facilitating the development of fair and effective regulations, and safeguarding individuals' privacy. Data Protection Authorities are interested in ensuring that data handling practices adhere to privacy regulations and protecting individuals' rights regarding their data. This (incomplete) list of stakeholder's interest shows the great demand for socio-economic data on agricultural land markets.

Table 1: Agricultural land market data sources (incomplete list), Source: DFG research unit FORLand

Data source	Regional coverage	Comment
Ackerbauliches Ertragspotential der Böden in Deutschland	Germany	
AFiD-Panel Agrarstruktur AFiD	Germany	
Agraratlas	Germany	
ALKIS - Amtliches Liegenschaftskataster- IS	Germany	FORLand internal access only[1]
LIKA - Liegenschaftskataster	Berlin, Brandenburg	
ASE - Agrarstrukturhebung	Germany	
Bodenrichtwertdatensatz GAA	German federal states	
BORIS-D Bodenrichtwerte Deutschland	BB	
BVVG tender results and rental prices	Eastern Germany	
BVVG tender results and rental prices	BB, MV, ST, SN, TH	For these Federal States FORLand internal access only
CORINE - Land Cover database of Europe	Europe	
CORINE - Land Cover 10 ha (CLC10)	Germany	
Dafne database	Germany	
DFBK - Digitales Feldblockkataster	B, BB	
DLM - Digitale Landschaftsmodelle	Germany	
FADN - Farm Accountancy Data Network	EU	
Handelsregister - Electronic commercial registers	Germany	
IACS - Integrated Administration and Control System	EU	
InVeKoS/IACS - Integriertes Verwaltungs- und Kontrollsystem	Germany, per federal state	BB, ST, NI (FORLand internal)
Kaufpreissammlungen (Obere) Gutachterausschüsse OGA	German federal states	BB, MV, ST, SN, TH (FORLand internal)
Landgesellschaften tender results	German federal states	ST (FORLand internal)
Land Matrix - public database	World	
Darstellungsdienst: LW Ertragspotenzial	BB	(WMS-LBGR-BOERTRAG)
LUCAS - Land cover/use statistics	EU	
Regionaldatenbank Deutschland	Germany	
Statistisches Bundesamt	Germany	

[1] Some data is not publicly available, e.g. only the FORLand team has access to the data for Märkisch Oderland.

Table 1 provides a list of relevant sources for agricultural land market data. The current system of (socio-economic) data sources on agricultural land markets in Germany and in Europe is highly heterogeneous: The data sources differ in terms of purpose, regional coverage, time period, data type, temporal as well as spatial resolution. Some are publicly available, typically at an aggregated level. Others are labelled as confidential with limited access for defined users. In many cases, data protection issues hinder access and reusability to the information of interest. The data provides a comprehensive overview of the various elements that shape agricultural systems, including soil qualities, yield data, land use and landscape models, land prices, and ownership structures. This information forms the foundation for our investigation into the close link between agricultural systems and economic information.

Against this background (high demand for land market data combined with remarkable heterogeneity), LASI overall aims, first, in adding these types of socio-economic information to the existing information on Agrosystems, and in establishing a link between these areas through the development of meta-databases and technical reports. The second goal is derived from the point that LASI oversees long-term, continuous field trial data. Long-term field experiments provide unique information about several major issues of present-day agriculture including adaptation to climate change, management of soil organic matter and environmentally sound fertilization. Key stakeholders are barely aware of the scientific outcome and the relevance of such experiments in particular because (i) data from long-term field experiments are often stored in databases where they are commonly inaccessible or at least unprocessed and thus incomprehensible and (ii) articles based on data from long-term field experiments are mainly published in peer-reviewed expert journals with little or no impact outside of the scientific community. As FAIRagro is an excellent platform for the dissemination of research activities, LASI attempts for novel approaches towards a FAIR access to the knowledge gathered from these field trials, and hereby directly establishes a connection between recent Agrosystem uses cases (see keyword 'Crop trial' in figure 1) the proposed new uses case. In combination with the primary socio-economic objectives of the UC, dissemination of research activities in field trials will contribute to the overall goals of increasing sustainability and economic efficiency of agricultural enterprises.

The specific objectives of the new UC LASI consist of:

- Systematization and evaluation of the current system of data sources on agricultural land markets regarding FAIRagro principles; Identification of opportunities to increase transparency in socio-economic agricultural land market data; Expansion of the scope of FAIRagro through the development of protocols for systematic meta-analyses and technical reports;
- Recording the status quo of the available information on the long-term field tests in form of publications in scientific or mainstream media and databases; Identification of channels for advanced communication and dissemination of crop field trials.

An example for meta-analyses is the work of Leonhardt et al. (2023) , who emphasize the increasing availability of land use data from the EU's Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) for research purposes. IACS data contain annual plot-level information on cultivation and location of the land farmed by agricultural beneficiaries, providing highly disaggregated spatial and temporal information. Leonhardt et al. advocate for a systematic review of the applications of IACS plot-level data to enhance the usability of this data for future research. Additionally, LASIS's contributions align with the technical methodologies of Müller et al. (2021), who explore the concentration of ownership in agricultural land using cadastral records to highlight the market power exerted by large landowners. They stress the importance of combining cadastral data with other registers to fully understand corporate structures' influence on local land markets. Furthermore, Schmitz and Müller (2020) contribute by providing an automated method to extract soil assessment data from ALKIS, thus offering comprehensive digital soil yield potential data across Germany, which can be pivotal for detailed land use and market analysis.

Regarding crop field trials LASI will connect to measure 2.1 (communicating and dissemination). LASI oversees data from 6 long-term, continuous field trials in Thyrow and 2 additional long-term field trials in Dahlem. LASI will facilitate communication and dissemination of data-related matters to the community via FAIRagro. Scientists from HUB have published numerous articles based on long-term data. For instance, Roß et al. (2022) investigated the effects of different fertilizing regimes on soil organic carbon contents and winter rye yields by utilizing data from the Thyrow long-term field experiment DIV.2. Kroschewski et al. (2022) studied the effect of crop rotation and straw application on soil carbon sequestration in the Thyrow long-term experiment DV. LASI anticipates that FAIRagro will serve as an optimal platform for the dissemination of research activities, particularly those that prioritize data-driven communication. The field trials in Thyrow and Dahlem are currently overseen by the Department of Crop and Animal Sciences, Prof. Timo Kautz).

In summary, increasing FAIR data management, increasing translucency in agricultural land market data, and extended access to field trial data create a ripple effect, positively impacting various stakeholders and contributing to the overall health and sustainability of the agricultural sector. FAIRagro will highly benefit from LASI. This also applies vice versa.

Scientific background, added expertise and preliminary work

LASI benefits from the outcomes of the DFG-funded project FORLAND. Amongst others, scientists from HUB (Odening), IAMO (Balmann), and the University of Göttingen (Mußhoff, Hüttel) utilize and (in parts) produce relevant socio-economic land market data. FORLand started to link Agrosystem data with socio-economic information and provide infrastructure for sustainable data documentation, storage, and transfer of jointly used data within the group as well as to external researchers. At the same time, the long-term field trials in Thyrow and Dahlem are currently overseen by the Department of Crop and Animal Sciences of HUB (Kautz). Relevant publications and products are:

FORLand Metadatabase.

https://www.agrar.hu-berlin.de/en/institut-en/departments/daoe/forland/publications/forland-metadatabase_external.pdf

Kroschewski, B., Richter, C., Baumecker, M., & Kautz, T. (2023). Effect of crop rotation and straw application in combination with mineral nitrogen fertilization on soil carbon sequestration in the Thyrow long-term experiment Thy_D5. *Plant and Soil*, 488(1), 121-136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-022-05459-5>

Leonhardt, H., Hüttel, S., Lakes, T., Wesemeyer, M., Wolff, S. (2023): Use Cases of the Integrated Administration and Control System's Plot-Level Data: Protocol and Pilot Analysis for a Systematic Mapping Review. *German Journal of Agricultural Economics* 72(3/4): 168-184. <https://doi.org/10.30430/giae.2023.0385>.

Müller, D., Rufin, P., Schwieder, M. (2021): Quantification of Ownership Concentration from Cadastral Records of Agricultural Land in Märkisch-Oderland. Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. FORLand Technical Paper 2-2021. <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.311013>.

Roß, C. L., Baumecker, M., Ellmer, F., & Kautz, T. (2022). Organic manure increases carbon sequestration far beyond the "4 per 1000 Initiative" goal on a sandy soil in the Thyrow long-term field experiment DIV. 2. *Agriculture*, 12(2), 170. <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0472/12/2/170>

Schmitz, T., Müller, D. (2020): Digitale Karte der Bodenwertzahlen für Brandenburg. Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. FORLand Technisches Papier 1-2020. <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.308812>.

UC specification and maturity

Research data management (RDM) is the process of planning, collecting, and storing data. This UC does not involve planning, collecting, or storing data. Instead, it evaluates the heterogeneous agricultural land market data regarding FAIR principles and makes suggestions for future collection and provision of data. A representative meta-analysis example in this context is Leonhardt et al. (2023), who did such an analysis for data from the EU's Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS). They provide a clear description of the links to IACS regarding "Spatial join," "Farm ID," and "municipality" for a vast set of data, including weather data (temperature, precipitation), Landsat satellite data, CORINE land-use cover layer, and more. The data includes species sampling data, a digital elevation model (topographic data), OpenStreetMap, regional planning data, municipality borders, soil quality rating/data, a digital cadastre map, a land register, farm accountancy data network (FADN) data, and agricultural structure survey (ASS) data. The following table is based on that example.

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Climatology, Geography, Soil science, Crop Science, Economics
Scales	Farms (Germany, EU), fields (plots), landscapes, regions, municipalities
Data domains	Weather data, soil, crop management data, crop growth and development, yield formation, farm accountancy data
Data types	Raw data components from IACS: Spatial information (Geometry, Plot size only, Location); Temporal information (Changes over time); Thematic information (Crop types, Land use classes, Landscape elements); tables, figures, texts, Other (Farm ID, Farmstead location, Ownership status, Soil quality, Topography), various data types*
File formats	In this example pdf, xlsx
Source data / database / repositories	In this example publications (peer reviewed journals, conference proceedings, crop science databases at Thae Institute, BonaRes Repository)
Processing workflows	Processing workflows Scoping review or a systematic mapping review
Tools/software	Reference management software Mendeley, Python Scripts, Search engines (Livivo, Web of Science, ProQuest, Science Direct) *

* At this point we would also like to refer to Müller (2021), who illuminate the concentration of agricultural land ownership by analysing cadastral records of agricultural land at a single point in time and for a single district in the federal state of Brandenburg. They process the cadastral data for subsequent analysis in GIS and with statistical software packages.

Likewise, the UC makes suggestions for future dissemination of long-term, continuous field trial data based on an evaluation of available information in form of publications or stored in databases and repositories.

The maturity of the UC can be described in respect to the technology readiness levels (TRL) as follows (see table below): Data protection issues are a central problem in socio-economic land market data. It is clear that personal data and data protection are challenging. Effective data protection measures are crucial for safeguarding individuals' privacy rights and maintaining trust in the digital ecosystem.

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	TRL 1 – basic principles observed
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated

We will start by addressing the basic principles and then we will formulate the corners of a technology concept that covers relevant sources (see table 1) for agricultural land market data.

Self-assessment of FAIRness status quo, data quality and legal aspects

LASI benefits greatly from the research of FORLand, which is also committed to the FAIR principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-Usable research data and results whenever possible. The recent database for agricultural land market data comprises inter alia: (i) transaction data for several German states provided by (Obere) Gutachterausschüsse für Grundstückswerte (OGA, GA); (ii) auction data from the BVVG and one state land trusts; (iii) cadastre data on land ownership for selected counties in Germany (ALKIS) and Austria; (iv) IACS data for Austria and several German Federal States; and (v) FADN data for Austria. These and other data have been provided by the respective authorities (e.g., OGAs, GA, BVVG, Ministries of Agriculture, and land surveying offices) to Principal Investigators for exclusive usage in their research projects based on individual agreements and cost provisions. The aforementioned institutions have the sole right of disposition about the data and are also responsible for data repository. This prevents FORLand, respective LASI from publishing these data or forwarding them to external researchers. Legal aspects play a major role in this kind of data sources. This complex issue is a great opportunity for improvement and further development. Overall, the status quo in addressing FAIR principles by LASI can be described as follows:

- Findable: Socio-economic agricultural land market data are very heterogenous. It can be challenging for those without insider knowledge to locate data that is of interest, given the absence of a common platform.
- Accessible: It is often the case that the protection of personal data can act as a barrier to fair access to information that is relevant to interested parties.
- Interoperable: Interoperability among agricultural land market data poses a significant challenge due to its inherent heterogeneity.
- Reusable: The reusability of agri. land market data is often hindered by various factors, including inconsistent formats, lack of standardization, and limited accessibility.

The following RDM elements are relevant: Metadata, licences, legal aspects, data quality.

Expected outcomes

The following outcomes are expected:

- Protocols for systematic meta-analyses and technical reports on agricultural land market data with focus on socio-economics
- Workshop (dissemination of results, stakeholder communication, see work plan)

Involvement of UC institutions

The University of Göttingen and IAMO play a pivotal role in supporting the LASI project due to their expertise in the analysis of agricultural land market data and as driving forces in the FORLand group. In particular, we expect Mußhoff to aid in empirical and experimental analysis of land rental rates and farmland prices, while Balmann will support us by evaluating the suitability of various data sources for use in agricultural land market policy-making processes. In particular, IAMO will assist in the assessment of the suitability of these data sources for decision-makers on laws and further legal aspects.

Associated partner	Contributions
Prof. Dr. Oliver Mußhoff (Georg-August-Universität Göttingen)	Assistance via sharing of expertise in empirical and experimental analysis of land rental rates and farmland prices How to manage data from economic experiments
Prof. Dr. Alfons Balmann (IAMO Halle)	Support by the evaluation of the suitability of various data sources for use in agricultural land market policy making processes. In particular, IAMO will help to assess the suitability of these data sources for decision makers on laws and further legal aspects.

The Balmann Team is comprised of experts with experience in processing cadastral data, with the objective of quantifying the concentration of ownership of agricultural land (see Müller et al., 2021).

UC - FAIRagro connection

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	UC will benefit	UC will contribute	Essential	Short explanation (in bullet points)
TA 2: Community Involvement & Networking				
Communication and dissemination	X		X	We want to learn from experiences of Measure 2.1. and 2.2.
Training and education		X		We will organize a Workshop at the end of the project.
TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality				
Standards for digital resources	X			To take up experience
Standards for data management	X			To take up experience
Measures for data quality and fitness for use	X			To take up experience
Data quality annotation and curation	X			To take up experience
FAIR workflows and FAIR Digital Objects	X			To take up experience
Legal framework and machine-actionable policies	X	X	X	We will learn from Measure 3.6, we want to contribute by including socio-economic data.
TA 4: Services				
Central Service (‘FAIRagro Portal’)	X			Always essential
Searchable inventory of services and data	X			To take up experience
FAIRagro Task Area 5: Overarching activities				
Internationalisation	X			Data Management in the EU context

UC requirements

We ask for support / collaboration in 3 directions:

1. We believe that a direct collaboration could build upon Task Area 1: Use Cases – Implementation, in particular Measure 1.4: UC4 - Learning from incomplete data. As this UC aims to improve availability and to complement results from long-term agricultural field experiments (LTE), we would like to cooperate with ZALF, ZB MED, UBN and TUM.
2. We want to learn from the experiences within Task Area 2: Community Involvement and Networking. In particular we demand for collaboration within Measure 2.1: Communication and Dissemination Contributors: JKI (lead) and Measure 2.2: Community Participation ATB (lead). We request your assistance in identifying contemporary tools and communication channels for disseminating research outcomes from field trials and associated data.
3. As Measure 3.6: Legal Framework and Machine-Actionable Policies (Contributors: FIZ (lead), SGN, KTBL) develops legal guidelines, policies, model agreements and legal metadata we see a straight link to a collaboration because of the complex legal issues related to agricultural land market data sources.

UC dissemination and Community engagement

Dissemination & community engagement

LASI's multifaceted approach encompasses several key strategies to achieve the objective to foster a cultural change towards a FAIR and collaborative RDM in agricultural research:

- The UC plays a crucial role in enhancing data accessibility and transparency by integrating socio-economic data into agrosystems and meticulously categorizing agricultural land market data sources.
- We strive to facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration by integrating socio-economic variables with Agrosystem-related information. This approach enables researchers from diverse backgrounds to collaborate and gain holistic insights into agri systems
- LASI is committed to pioneering the development of meta-databases and technical reports. This work aims to promote standardization and interoperability of research data while upholding FAIR principles.
- Finally, this UC advocates for FAIR communication of long-term field trial data, encouraging transparent and equitable sharing practices.

Overall, LASI's concerted efforts align closely with FAIRagro's mission, aiming to enhance the quality and accessibility of research data while fostering a culture of openness, transparency, and collaboration among agricultural researchers. Through LASI's initiatives, researchers are encouraged to share findings and contribute to collective knowledge advancement in the agricultural domain.

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

A one-year work programme was drawn up:

Objective 1: Systematization and Evaluation of Agricultural Land Market Data

Actions:

- Conduct a comprehensive review of existing data sources on agricultural land markets, including public datasets, confidential sources, and proprietary databases.
- Evaluate the compliance of these data sources with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles.
- Identify gaps, inconsistencies, and challenges in the current system of data sources.
- Engage with stakeholders to gather feedback and insights on their data needs and challenges.
- Develop a report summarizing the findings and recommendations for improving data accessibility, quality, and transparency.

Objective 2: Expansion of FAIRagro Scope and Communication of Field Trial Data

Actions:

- Identify opportunities to integrate socio-economic agricultural land market data into FAIRagro.
- Develop protocols for systematic meta-analyses and technical reports to facilitate access to and understanding of agricultural land market data.
- Establish channels for communication and dissemination of long-term field trial data.
- Collaborate with FAIRagro platform developers to implement changes and updates.
- Promote FAIR communication of field trial data through targeted outreach and awareness campaigns.

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
M1	Conduct data review and initial evaluation	1-2
M2	Engage stakeholders and gather feedback	3-4
M3	Develop and finalize the report on agricultural land market data	5-6
M4	Implement integration plan for socio-economic data into FAIRagro	7-8
M5	Establish communication channels, launch dissemination efforts, and promote FAIR communication of field trial data	9-12

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
D1	Report (systematization and evaluation of agricultural land market data)	3
D2	Integration plan (for incorporating socio-economic data into FAIRagro)	6
D3	Outreach material (promoting FAIR communication of field trial data)	9
D4	Final Report (Recommendations for enhancing data accessibility and transparency); Workshop	12

This one-year work programme outlines a structured approach to achieving the objectives of systematizing and evaluating agricultural land market data, as well as expanding the scope of FAIRagro and enhancing communication of field trial data. By implementing these actions, LASI aims to address the pressing need for improved access to socio-economic data on agricultural land markets and facilitate the dissemination of valuable research findings to stakeholders and interested parties.

5 Diving into arable weed data to link biodiversity and farming “WeeDive”

Applicant: **Prof. Dr. Bärbel Gerowitt** (University of Rostock, DAFA)

Additional associated partner: Dr. Christoph von Redwitz (Julius Kühn-Institut – Bundesforschungsinstitut für Kulturpflanzen, JKI)

Running time: 12 months, Jan 2025-Dec 2025

Keywords: Monitoring, Long-term experiment (LTE), reference inventory

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

WeeDive focuses on weeds in arable farming, the occurrence of species affected by management, and possible contributions to biodiversity. Data sources on different time and spatial scales are required. WeeDive strives to make three types of data available for open access. The data types vary by nature due to the sampling method used. WeeDive addresses RDM in agrosystem research and develops and tests a service to overcome the challenges of no access, buried data and scattered knowledge.

We will (1) add to a European monitoring data format, “Arable Weeds and Management in Europe” (AWME), and (2) develop a format for long-term experimental (LTE) data on weeds under management options that allow weed survival in crops, (3) offer a reference inventory to modify weed management for biodiversity goals. A (4) comprehensive example will be derived of how these data can enable and assist scientific exercises, e.g., about changes in weeds on time scales relevant to climate change or on spatial scales relevant to IPM decisions in farming. Thus, WeeDive strategically offers knowledge to join food security and biodiversity conservation goals in arable management. Besides adapting data format and management to FAIR principles, data curation will be safeguarded by hand-shake activities of the project partners.

Access to the three data collections will help to address future questions in agriculture. Moreover, all data types used in WeeDive can be applied to related issues, e.g., monitoring herbicide-resistant weeds, accessing more LTE on arable management, or linking up with other services (e.g., soil erosion and soil structure).

UC concept and objectives

WeeDive addresses three types of long-term weed data on a spatial gradient, organises their open access and suggests how to produce added value with them.

Weed species in arable farming are **monitored** field-wise to detect changes on various time and space scales. A European volunteer initiative of weed scientists being members of the European Weed Research Society (EWRS) created an open-access database (AWME). Both WeeDive partners are members of this initiative. AWME is a database of primary arable weed vegetation records from across Europe. The database currently contains 273,650 occurrence records, each comprising a list of species found on a plot from an arable field. Unique is that field management data is included. AWME is currently hosted in the UK but currently not curated. University of Rostock holds data from recent surveys in Germany and Northern Europe suitable for being added. WeeDive will add these new monitoring data to the AWME database (Bensch et al. 2024, Andert et al. 2023, Hofmeijer et al. 2022). The surveys followed different protocols. Therefore, the data needs preparation to be added. Within WeeDive the technical standard of AWME will be kept. Data from Central and Northern Europe, excluding Mediterranean areas, will build the core to add the new data. Analyses of these data can reflect weed species change under different management options on the spatial scale of Central and Northern Europe.

Partner Gerowitt owns comprehensive data of an **LTE** in Central Germany. Treatments with IPM-control options for weeds to survive in crops according to thresholds were established in

a rotation. Long-term rotational and management effects were investigated in a randomized design. Twenty-year data recorded all species and densities in the vegetation as well as in the soil seed bank. Field data of this duration and detail are extremely rare. Nevertheless, the dataset was not yet analysed for weed species changes under the management treatments carried out. Rather the population dynamic of a selected species was described in two publications from 1998 and 2002. Currently, these data are buried and almost not accessible. Raw data, including replicats of the treatments and extensive false replicats in each plot during the years, are kept in a vast number of individual dbf-files. A state-of-art technical data structure suitable for open access will be developed. Data will be quality-checked and transferred. Analyses of these data can reflect changes in weed species under different management options on the spatial scale of Central Germany.

University of Rostock is currently investigating in a project granted by the German Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN) how weed economic thresholds can be modified for biodiversity-producing ecosystem services. References in international databases, publications and collections were searched for common arable weed species of temperate zones (excluding tropical, subtropical and dryland production conditions), structured and fed into an **inventory**. Actually, the WeeDive partners share this inventory to derive methods to model the biodiversity benefit of weeds. For this purpose, the weed species are connected to different ecosystem services within the inventory. Open access to this inventory would obviously save time for other scientists. Moreover, adding more references in a controlled process could improve the collection. Currently, the inventory is organised as an xlsx-file with species, bibliographies of the references and assigned ecosystem services. These inventory data can help to reflect biodiversity issues in management decisions. These decisions are undertaken on a local field scale.

At the end of the UC process, WeeDive offers new access to existing data, technically independent from each other. The “Monitoring” and “Inventory” types can be foreseen to be further publicly added. Conceptual exercises, e.g., changes in weeds on a time scale relevant to climate change or on a spatial scale relevant to IPM decisions in farming, are undertaken on information derived from the three data types. These exercises will feed a publication (working title: How weed data varying in space can assist in linking farming and biodiversity).

Objectives:

- Organise open public access for future use of three data collections on arable weed species
- Produce additional value from the existing European monitoring data
- Initiate utilization of long-term experimental (LTE) data on weeds under management options that allow weed survival in crops
- Offer a reference inventory with information necessary to modify weed management for biodiversity goals.
- Encourage scientists with advice on how the data could be used in a publication
- Safeguard data curation by hand-shake activities of the two project partners

Scientific background, added expertise and preliminary work

Bärbel Gerowitt is a senior weed researcher, curating German weed monitoring data and data from an LTE (1981-2002) on weed vegetation change through management, highly valuable but mainly buried (publications from 1998 and 2002 focusing on one species). Recently, the group collected sources to account for the biodiversity benefits of weeds.

Christoph v. Redwitz is a JKI weed researcher with a domain in model applications to weeds. Both partners collaborated in setting up the AWME database, hosted at Rothamsted, UK; Redwitz was one of the key players. Currently, a lack of curating in the UK prevents expansions.

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UC specification and maturity

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Agronomy, Plant Protection, Vegetation Science
Scales	Plant, crop trial, field, farm, region
Data domains	Arable vegetation, crop management, services of weeds
Data types	Tabular data, Bibliographic data
File formats	Open, dbf (LTE), xlsx (inventory)
Source data / database / repositories	LTE, Bibliographic data, European Database “Arable Weeds and Management in Europe” (AWME)
Processing workflows	Concept
Tools/software	Open, R

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	<p>TRL 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> independent monitoring data are published in aggregated analyses, no open access to data LTE data are collected, access to data is limited to one person sources for service inventory are researched, no open and joint use of the data
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	<p>TRL 4</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> data are available for open and joint use. an example application is performed technical recommendation for future use

Self-assessment of FAIRness status quo, data quality and legal aspects

WeeDive strives to make data easily and openly accessible, either as a dedicated data repository or as a query-able website application.

- The Arable Weeds and Management in Europe database includes weed species and metadata to describe the agronomic site management. Set up as a PostgreSQL database hosted in Rothamsted, UK, there is currently a lack of curation. To overcome this current situation, WeeDive will extract data from Central Europe and process and add new data from Germany. Governing and sharing rules are in place; ownership of the contributed datasets remains with the providers. Restricted access is possible to comply with anonymity agreements (not sharing farmer fields' exact locations) or institutional policies. The new data from Germany can flow back to the UK host.
- Data type "LTE" will be made available as raw data whenever appropriate. Data and metadata are the property of a partner. Data quality is high, except for some gaps due to weather or accidental circumstances. Nevertheless, quality checks will be needed.
- The inventory of ecosystem services for weed species offspring a research project funded by BfN. The funder has no property in the data. Rather, BfN encourages making the inventory publicly available. However, more references may occur when more weed species are included (actually restricted to arable species common in Germany).

Expected outcomes

The major outcome is three open-source data collections. All software used will be open-source. The code developed for data processing will probably be managed on a public repository (e.g., Github).

More specific outcome:

- Workflow to expand AWME with new data, delivering advice about what to do if new arable weed monitoring data are generated
- Public LTE data on arable management effects on weed vegetation. Twenty years of repeated measurements on weed species in a randomized design with weed control treatments fed into a data repository, probably deployed using CKAN, a widely used data repository software implementing the DCAT standard
- Usable inventory of ecosystem services by weeds openly accessible and addable.
- Safeguarded future data curation
- Peer-reviewed publication: How long-term arable weed data varying in space can assist in linking biodiversity and farming

Involvement of UC institutions

Partner	Role	Responsibility	Contribution
University of Rostock, Bärbel Gerowitt	Data donator, current curator, senior weed expert	Supervise workflow, explain data background, Merge existing data types with FAIRagro demands	<p>Weed species in arable farming monitored field-wise together with field management data. Data from recent surveys in Germany and Northern Europe suitable for being added (Bensch et al 2023, Andert et al. 2022, Hofmeijer et al. 2021) but not yet included in the AWME database</p> <p>Own LTE data, twenty years, treatments allowing weeds to survive due to thresholds, rotational and long-term population effects, data about species, densities and population development. (for one selected species by Gerowitt 1998, 2002, J. Plant Dis & Prot).</p> <p>Inventory of ecosystem services of weeds (Bensch et al. 2024). International references (databases, publications, collections) for temperate zones collected for ecosystem services of weed species. Inventory to derive methods to model biodiversity benefit of weeds in economic thresholds.</p>
JKI, Christoph v. Redwitz	Data recipient and future curator, weed scientist (permanent)	New set-up following FAIRagro principles AWME contact	<p>Experienced in R and open-source software (Redwitz & de Mol 2021)</p> <p>Key player in setting up the AWME database</p>

UC - FAIRagro connection

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	UC will benefit	UC will contribute	Essential	Short explanation (in bullet points)
TA 2: Community Involvement & Networking				
Communication and dissemination	X			WeeDive will reach wider audience
Training and education	X			Young scientists in WeeDive will profit
TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality				
Standards for digital resources	X	X		Integration of the AWME and the LTE data
Standards for data management		X		Improved findability of digital resources by establishing access to the LTE
Measures for data quality and fitness for use				Data about arable management will be adapted to standards
Data quality annotation and curation	X		X	Perspective in curation for sustainable research data life cycle
Other... Representing a wide spectrum of applications		X	X	Having an UC dealing with arable weeds and their importance in IPM
TA 4: Services				
Searchable inventory of services and data	X			Findability of the UC data in the central search service of FAIRagro
FAIRagro Task Area 5: Overarching activities				
Internationalisation		X	X	WeeDive contributes with a direct link to the European AWME data-base and the European Weed Research Society
Cross-NFDI networking	X		X	WeeDive would benefit from already existing cross NFDI-networking in FAIR-agro to NFDI4BioDiversity activities

UC requirements

TA1: Include and emphasize processing of long-term data on arable weeds as a challenge for agricultural systems

WeeDive fills an obvious gap in FAIRagro-UCs completing IPM issues for arable weeds. Vegetation surveys traditionally deliver large datasets, and scientists like access to these data. WeeDive focuses on arable weeds, widens the information on arable management and can profit from the collaboration in agricultural science.

TA2: Support community involvement of European weed scientists organised in EWRS and create structures for networking activities in order to make the national and international weed community aware of WeeDive.

FAIRagro would assist to keep the AWME database vital for European weed scientists. WeeDive would benefit from already existing cross-NFDI networking in FAIRagro to NFDI4Biodiversity activities.

TA3: Advice on FAIR standards, interim evaluation of the data structure in WeeDive and final review of compliance with FAIR standards at the end of the project

WeeDive would benefit from standards for management labels in monitoring and LTE data. This would foster linked analyses.

TA5: Safeguard administration, scaling up and down, support transnational research activities

Besides open access, a perspective in curation is vital for a sustainable research data life cycle. WeeDive would benefit from being embedded into FAIRagro.

UC dissemination and Community engagement

Dissemination & community engagement

WeeDive contributes to promoting and implementing FAIR RDM in academic societies. WeeDive integrates diverse types of data and creates public data formats:

- to standardise collection and management practices,
- to make data better accessible.
- to ensure greater interoperability and reusability.

WeeDive's final concept will facilitate:

- scientific exercises to model long-term changes,
- addressing broader ecological and agricultural challenges
- enabling the support of more effective weed management strategies aligned with biodiversity conservation.

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

Action 1: AWME long-term monitoring data - using and adding new data from Central Europe

JKI – contact AWME, extract records for Central and Northern Europe, expand with data from the Rostock group, harmonise format, back-up AWME after expansion; University of Rostock, prepare and upload new data

Action 2: LTE data in Central Germany – saving buried data for generic use

University of Rostock, sifting buried LTE data (1981-2002), checking data quality, adapting quality for different use; JKI, specify the technical structure, implanting salvaged data

Action 3: Biodiversity services of arable weeds – providing inventory data

University of Rostock, user manual about required information for new references; JKI, specify the technical structure, preparing the procedure for open public additions

Action 4: Concept for Use and Data Curation – outlining an example

JKI, describing an example, lead authoring publication; University of Rostock, co-authoring publication

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
M1	AWME expanded by new data	3
M2	LTE buried data lifted, managed for quality	6
M3	Structure built for inventory on ecosystem services of weeds	9
M4	Proposal for public use developed	11

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
D1	Updated AWME curated for Germany by JKI	6
D2	Report on the data quality of the LTE, including proposals for the use	9
D3	Catalog (CKAN) for LTE-data	10
D4	Manuscript from WeeDive (How long-term arable weed data varying in space can assist in linking biodiversity and farming)	12

6 Systematic Approaches for Efficient Data Synchronization in Horticultural Sciences “HortSEEDS”

Applicant: **Dr. André Sradnick** (Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops, IGZ)

Involved persons: Prof. Dr. Nicole van Dam, Babette Regierer (Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops, IGZ)

Running time: 6 months, Nov 2024-Apr 2025

Keywords: data workflow, horticultural research data, data integration, heterogenous datasets

UC description and scientific details

Short UC summary (Abstract)

Integrating lab and field data in agricultural and horticultural research presents challenges due to differences in the spatial and temporal dimensions as well as size and formats of the different datasets. Laboratory-based analyses, such as transcriptomic or metabolic analyses, often generate datasets with many variables providing detailed insights in mechanisms underlying plant responses to the environment which also determine vegetable crop performance. It is challenging to combine these large and detailed datasets with data collected in greenhouse and open field experiments. In the latter, continuous sensor data (e.g. weather data, soil humidity), soil data (N,P,K) and insect and microbial community data are commonly generated. Especially for vegetable cultures, such data are generated at a much more fine-grained and temporally denser scale than in field crops. Developing a standardised workflow is thus crucial to harmonize these different data for proper sharing and further processing. This requires the development of consistent protocols for data collection, ensuring compatibility of data obtained by different approaches, and employing robust analytical methods that account for different data scales and sources. To establish and adapt a standardised workflow for horticultural experiments in this use case pilot we will use the metabolic, sensor, and biological data generated in a joint field experiment, GreenCycle, carried out at IGZ. At the end of this pilot, we will have produced a first prototype for harmonizing data and metadata by standardized ontologies and workflows, which may serve as a blueprint for horticultural sciences.

UC concept and objectives

User case

A field experiment at the KPA (box plot setup) at IGZ assesses the impact of diverse fertilizer management strategies on different soil types during biannual mustard cultivation. The study focuses on nutrient management, greenhouse gas emissions, and biodiversity impacts, aiming to enhance understanding of sustainable agricultural practices and their environmental consequences. This research involves multiple working groups at IGZ: HORTSYS, BIOTIC, and QUALITY, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration to address complex horticultural challenges.

1. Comprehensive Workflow Development

Objective: Standardize protocols combining good laboratory (GLP) and agricultural (GAP) practices.

- **Harmonized Protocols:** Develop protocols suitable for both lab and field settings.
- **Training:** Provide integrated practices training.
- **Automation:** Implement systems for consistent data collection and analysis.

2. Data Transfer and Integration Support

Objective: Facilitate data integration from lab to field in horticulture.

- **Standardized Formats:** Establish formats for plant-soil-microorganism-insects data.
- **Evaluate Existing Databases:** Assess current databases to avoid duplication and contribute to FAIRagro.
- **Transformation Tools:** Utilize tools for seamless data transfer and use.

3. Assurance of Data Quality

Objective: Ensure data integrity across lab and field studies.

- **Quality Control:** Implement tailored data quality assessment protocols.
- **Version Control:** Track data modifications to ensure transparency.
- **Collaborative Platforms:** Enhance interdisciplinary communication.

4. Data Transparency and Accessibility

Objective: Enhance findings' transparency and accessibility.

- **Documentation:** Detail methodologies and results for horticulture applications.
- **Interdisciplinary Engagement:** Organize workshops to bridge research and practice.
- **Visualization Tools:** Develop aids for data interpretation.
- **Open Data Initiatives:** Implement open data sharing policies.

Scientific background, added expertise and preliminary work

André Sradnick specializes in soil plant nutrition for open field vegetables and soil biology, with a strong background in modelling and experimental design.

Sradnick, A., Werner, M., and Körner, O. (2023). Make a choice: A rapid strategy for minimizing peat in horticultural press pots substrates using a constrained mixture design and surface response approach. *PLoS One* 18, e0289320.

Sradnick, A., Murugan, R., Oltmanns, M., Raupp, J., and Joergensen, R. G. (2013). Changes in functional diversity of the soil microbial community in a heterogeneous sandy soil after long-term fertilization with cattle manure and mineral fertilizer. *Applied Soil Ecology* 63, 23-28.

Nicole van Dam is an expert in molecular and chemical analyses for plant resistance to herbivory.

Marr, S., Hageman, J. A., Wehrens, R., van Dam, N. M., Bruelheide, H., & Neumann, S. (2021). LC-MS based plant metabolic profiles of thirteen grassland species grown in diverse neighbourhoods. *Scientific Data*, 8(1). doi:10.1038/s41597-021-00836-8

Babette Regierer is the scientific coordinator developing the Research Data Management strategies at IGZ. She has experience in standardisation strategies.

Hollmann S, Kremer A, Baebler Š, Trefois C, Gruden K, Rudnicki WR, Tong W, Gruca A, Bongcam-Rudloff E, Evelo CT, Nechyporenko A, Frohme M, Šafránek D, Regierer B, D'Elia D. 2020. The need for standardisation in life science research - an approach to excellence and trust. *F1000Res*. 2020 Dec 4;9:1398. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.27500.2.

Jointly, the IGZ team brings expertise in horticultural experiments and the concomitant data challenges to FAIRagro.

UC specification and maturity

Category	Description: UC specification and examples
Disciplines	Horticulture, Chemical Ecology
Scales	From molecule to field
Data domains	Weather, soil, crop management, plant growth, leaf gas exchange, plant microbiome, metabolome, volatilome, genome and transcriptome, flowering, diseases and pests, nutrient dynamics
Data types	Tabular data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - volatile and non-volatile metabolomic datasets (m/z features), meteorological data, data on insect communities, data on microbial communities, greenhouse gas soil emission data, soil mineralisation data property data, chlorophyll levels, plant biomass, drone images
File formats	*.csv, *.xlsx, open weather data, *.png,
Source data / database / repositories	Own data, DWD, FAIRagro RDI, OpenAgrar, Metabolights (metabolomics),
Processing workflows	concept
Tools/software	R, Python

	Description: UC specification
TRL of UC today	TRL 1
TRL of UC after completion of UC Project/ Pilot	TRL 2, max TRL

Self-assessment of FAIRness status quo, data quality and legal aspects

Findable:

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Each dataset in FAIRagro is assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to ensure it can be easily found and cited, e.g., a dataset on soil nutrient levels has a unique DOI.

Metadata: Uses comprehensive metadata standards such as the Dublin Core or ISO 19115 to enhance discoverability, e.g., a dataset on crop yields includes metadata detailing the location, time, and methods of data collection.

Accessible:

Licences: Implements standardized licenses like Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0) to define usage rights clearly, e.g., a weather dataset is available under a CC BY 4.0 license, allowing for broad use while giving proper credit to the creators.

Interoperable:

Standards: Adopts common data standards such as ISO/TC 211 for geographic information, ensuring compatibility across platforms, e.g., soil moisture data is stored in a standardized format compatible with GIS software.

Ontologies: Employs domain-specific ontologies like AGROVOC to standardize terminology, e.g., using AGROVOC terms for plant species and soil types to ensure consistency and ease of data integration.

Reusable:

Data Quality Checks: Implements rigorous quality control measures, such as validation protocols and peer review processes, to ensure data reliability, e.g., crop and soil state data undergoes multiple validation steps before publication.

Metadata: Provides detailed metadata to enable proper understanding and reuse of data, e.g., a pest occurrence dataset includes metadata on the collection methods, environmental conditions, and data processing steps.

Relevant RDM elements include:

Ensuring data accuracy, consistency, and reliability through systematic quality checks, e.g., performing outlier detection and correction on field data.

Adhering to legal and ethical standards, including data privacy and intellectual property rights, e.g., anonymizing sensitive data related to farm locations before sharing.

Reflection and Integration into FAIRagro:

The UC demonstrates strong adherence to FAIR principles through the use of PIDs, comprehensive metadata, and legal compliance. However, there is room for improvement in harmonizing metadata standards and enhancing interoperability through broader adoption of standardized ontologies.

Potential Improvements:

Achieving greater uniformity in metadata standards across highly heterogeneous datasets related to vegetable cultures. This includes the development of a unified metadata schema encompassing all aspects of crop-related data, including metabolomics, through the integration or consolidation of data ontologies.

Increasing the use of shared ontologies and PIDs to improve data integration and reuse, e.g., integrating more datasets with AGROVOC terms and ensuring all datasets have DOIs.

Expected outcomes

Standardized Workflow:	A standardized workflow for data collection and analysis, facilitating integration of lab and field data.
Analytical Tools:	Development of robust analytical tools for harmonizing and analyzing multi-scale datasets.
Metadata Standards:	Established metadata standards tailored to horticultural research, enhancing data interoperability.
Ontologies and Vocabularies:	Standardized ontologies and vocabularies for consistent data annotation and integration among different datasets.
Community Guidelines:	Guidelines for best practices in data management, integration, and sharing within the research community.
Recommendations:	Recommendations for improving data quality and ensuring compliance with FAIR principles in horticultural research.
Collaborative Platform:	Gain knowledge of collaborative platforms for sharing data, tools, and workflows, fostering community engagement and collaboration.

Involvement of UC institutions

N/A

UC - FAIRagro connection

UC contributions and benefits

FAIRagro Connection through respective TAs and focal points	UC will benefit	UC will contribute	Essential	Short explanation (in bullet points)
TA 2: Community Involvement & Networking				
Needs collection and evaluation	X	X	X	<p>Benefit: Gain insights from community feedback to refine UC methodologies and outputs.</p> <p>Contribute: Participate in surveys and provide feedback to help shape FAIRagro's future initiatives.</p>
Training and education	X		X	<p>Benefit: Training modules on workflow, guidelines etc.</p>
TA 3: Standardization, Interoperability & Quality				
Standards for digital resources	X	X		<p>Benefit: Access to established standards ensuring consistency & interoperability of data.</p> <p>Contribute: Implement and test these standards within the UC to provide feedback and case studies.</p>
Standards for data management	X	X		<p>Benefit: Adoption of best practices for data management, enhancing data usability and longevity.</p> <p>Contribute: Share UC-specific data management protocols to enrich FAIRagro's collection of best practices.</p>
FAIRagro Task Area 5: Overarching activities				
Cross-NFDI networking	X	X	X	<p>Benefit: Opportunities for cross-disciplinary collaboration and data sharing.</p> <p>Contribute: Engage with other NFDI initiatives to share insights and best practices from the UC.</p>

UC requirements

Integrating molecular (cellular processes) and field data (environment, pests) in agriculture is challenging due to inherent differences in scale and variability. A standardized workflow is proposed to bridge this gap, ensuring consistent data collection, compatible measurement techniques, and robust analysis methods that account for data scale. This will enhance research outcomes, validate lab findings in real-world fields, and improve knowledge transfer to practical agricultural strategies.

This project aligns with UC1 ("genotype-environment-management interactions") and UC6 ("automated data flows for crop simulation models"). Collaboration can be highly beneficial if databases/repositories and tools either already existing or developed within FAIRagro can be accessed and validated for the requirements of the HortSEEDS approach:

UC1 Data Infrastructure: Our workflow can leverage UC1's infrastructure to capture genotype-environment interactions, potentially informing and validating UC6's models.

UC6 Crop Simulation Models: Our standardized approach can contribute to seamless data flow for UC6 models, leading to more accurate predictions for farmers.

By working together, this effort has the potential to empower farmers in the future with data-driven insights for optimizing crop management and ultimately achieving sustainable and productive agricultural practices even under climate change conditions.

UC dissemination and Community engagement

Dissemination & community engagement

Point	Aim
All contribute to the development of the workflow:	Encourage collaborative development of standardized data workflows, leveraging diverse expertise.
Training in RDM and the new blueprint:	Provide specialized training programs in Research Data Management (RDM) and the newly developed workflow at IGZ to enhance skills and knowledge for horticultural researchers.
Connect to UC 1 and UC 6:	Foster collaboration and synergy with UC 1 and UC 6 to integrate efforts and streamline data management practices across units.
Connect to other horticulture research groups:	Expand collaborations with other research groups to refine and standardize the workflow, promoting widespread adoption.

Workplan

Actions (Work packages)

WP 1: Standardized Workflow Development

WP 1 focuses on developing a standardized workflow for integrating lab and field data to ensure compatibility and consistency across different settings. By defining common data standards, harmonizing protocols for data collection and metadata recording, implementing compatible measurement techniques, and developing robust analytical methods, we aim for enhanced integration and comparability of data from lab experiments and field studies. This facilitates more reliable analysis and interpretation, leading to improved insights into horticultural practices and environmental impacts.

WP 2: Automated Data Management

WP 2 aims to automate data processing, storage and quality checks, resulting in streamlined data management and enhanced data reliability. The creation of digital objects for data management, automated data storage solutions adhering to FAIR principles, in the relevant specialized public repositories, and automated plausibility checks contribute to improved efficiency and accuracy in handling large volumes of data. The outcome is a more efficient research process, with reduced manual effort in data management and increased confidence in data integrity.

WP 3: Knowledge Sharing and Collaboration

WP 3 focuses on promoting knowledge sharing and collaboration among researchers, stakeholders, and policymakers. By organizing workshops, seminars, and developing educational resources, the outcome is widespread dissemination of project findings and best practices in integrating lab and field data. Establishing a publicly accessible data repository enhances transparency and accessibility of research outputs, fostering further analysis and application of findings. Engaging with policymakers ensures that research insights contribute to informed decision-making and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

The outcomes include improved data compatibility and reliability, enhanced research efficiency, widespread dissemination of knowledge, and informed policy decisions benefiting agricultural sustainability.

Milestones

#	Milestone (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
M1	Define common data standards and harmonized protocols for data collection across lab and field settings in cooperation with UC 1 and UC 6.	3
M2	Implement automated workflows for data processing, storage solutions adhering to FAIR principles, and automated quality checks.	4
M3	First pilot workshop for testing concept and appropriateness at IGZ; this builds the basis to organize workshops, develop educational resources, explore and identify existing public data repositories most suitable to disseminate findings and promote collaboration among researchers and relevant FAIRagro UCs.	4

Deliverables

#	Deliverable (Name and description)	Achieved after x month
D1	Document outlining standardized data protocols for lab and field data integration.	3
D2	Implementation of an automated data processing workflow.	4
D3	A report specifying a blue print for data management in horticultural research and training.	6